

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND ANTIMICROBIAL POTENTIALS OF AQUEOUS LEAVES EXTRACT OF *MORINGA OLEIFERA* L AGAINST SELECTED CLINICAL PATHOGENS

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Abstract: This study investigated the phytochemical composition, nutritional, and antimicrobial properties of aqueous leaf extracts of *Moringa oleifera* using qualitative and quantitative analyses. Qualitative and quantitative analyses of aqueous extracts was conducted and antimicrobial efficacy was tested against selected bacterial and fungal pathogens using agar well diffusion and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) assays. Results revealed the presence of diverse bioactive compounds: alkaloids (1.0 % w/w), flavonoids (80.10 mg QE/g), saponins (6.20 %w/w), phenolics (110.8 mg GAE/g), steroids (0.7 mg CE/g), glycosides (5.8 mg GE/g), and terpenoids (4.3 % w/w) with significant inhibitory effects on fungi: *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus tamari*, *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, *Penicillium marneffeii*, *Myrothecium verrucaria*, *Rhizopus nigrican*, *Rhizopus stolonifera*, *Fuussarium oxysporum*, *Fussarium solani*, *Candida albicans* and bacteria: *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Serrtia marcescens*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Erwinia carotovora*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The high inhibitory effects of the extract, ranging from 52.24 ± 0.01 mm (*Erwinia carotovora*) at 100 mg/mL to 4.87 ± 0.02 mm (*Aspergillus niger*) at 25 mg/mL correlates with its high phenolic and flavonoid content. The MIC ranged from 6.25 mg/mL (*A. niger*, *A. flavus*, *A. tamari*, *B. theobromae*, and *P. marneffeii*) to 3.13 mg/mL (other isolates). These findings suggest that *M. oleifera* possesses promising natural antimicrobial agents that could serve as alternatives to synthetic drugs.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera*, phytochemicals, antimicrobial activity, natural products, bioactive compounds.

1.0 Introduction

Plants have long been recognized as valuable sources of bioactive compounds used in traditional medicine and modern therapeutics. The rise in multidrug-resistant microorganisms has renewed interest in plant-derived antimicrobials as safer, cost-effective alternatives. *Moringa oleifera*, commonly known as the drumstick tree or horseradish tree, is a fast-growing tropical plant belonging to the family *Moringaceae* (Ademiluyi et al., 2018; Othman et al., 2019). *Moringa oleifera* is widely distributed in Africa and Asia and is used traditionally for treating infections, inflammation, and malnutrition. The leaves are one of the most intensively studied parts of the plant because they

concentrate a wide array of secondary metabolites with nutritional and pharmacological relevance (Wang et al., 2024; Arshad et al., 2025).

Modern chromatographic and spectrometric methods (HPLC/UPLC-MS, GC-MS, LC-MS/MS, NMR) have identified hundreds of distinct compounds; however, these can be grouped into a smaller set of major chemical classes that account for most of the leaves' bioactivity and nutritional value (Rojas-Armas et al., 2024; Fitri et al., 2025). Key compound families include phenolic acids, flavonoids, glucosinolates and their isothiocyanate derivatives, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, terpenoids and sterols, carotenoids and tocopherols, and a notable suite of vitamins, amino acids, fatty acids, and minerals which contribute to its pharmacological properties, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory activities (El-Sherbiny et al., 2014; Gharsallah et al., 2023). However, the relationship between the phytochemical constituents and antimicrobial potential varies with solvent extraction and organism tested. This study aimed to qualitatively and quantitatively assess the phytochemical profile of *M. oleifera* leaf extracts and to evaluate their nutritional and antimicrobial potentials against selected pathogenic microorganisms.

1.1 Major phytochemical classes and representative compounds of *Moringa oleifera* leaves

1.1.1 Phenolic acids

Phenolic acids in *Moringa oleifera* leaves include chlorogenic acid (3-O-caffeoylquinic acid), caffeic acid, gallic acid, ferulic acid and sinapic acid (Hassan, 2021; Wang et al., 2024). These low-molecular-weight phenolics contribute substantially to antioxidant activity and are readily quantified by HPLC-DAD or LC-MS methods (Rojas-Armas et al., 2024). Studies report chlorogenic acid and related caffeoylquinic derivatives as abundant and important for free-radical scavenging (Ali et al., 2020).

1.1.2 Flavonoids

Flavonoids are among the most abundant polyphenols in the leaves. Notable flavonols and flavones include quercetin (and its glycosides), kaempferol (and glycosides), rutin (quercetin-3-O-rutinoside), myricetin, apigenin, and vicenin-2. These compounds are linked to antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cardioprotective effects *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Patil et al., 2022; Chis et al., 2023). Quantities vary with cultivar, season, and extraction solvent; quercetin and kaempferol derivatives are frequently the major flavonoids detected (Srivastava & Ganjewala, 2024).

1.1.3 Glucosinolates and isothiocyanates (*Moringin* family)

Moringa oleifera is unusual among edible leafy plants because it contains a suite of glucosinolates (sulfur-containing glycosides) and their hydrolysis products, isothiocyanates, which show potent bioactivities. The major glucosinolate in leaves is glucomoringin (4-(α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy)benzyl glucosinolate); on enzymatic hydrolysis (myrosinase), it produces moringin (4-(α -L-rhamnopyranosyloxy)benzyl isothiocyanate) and related isothiocyanates such as niazimicin and niazirin derivatives — compounds often credited with anticancer, antiinflammatory and

chemopreventive properties. Analytical detection commonly uses LC-MS and targeted UPLC-QTOF (Rojas-Armas et al., 2024; Engsuwana et al., 2024).

1.1.4 Alkaloids

Leaves of *Moringa oleifera* contain several low-abundance alkaloids (nitrogenous bases) that have been reported in qualitative screens (e.g., tests for alkaloids, GC-MS detection of specific nitrogen-containing metabolites). Alkaloids contribute to the plant's bioactivity profile but are generally present at lower concentrations than flavonoids and phenolics (Hassan, 2021; Rojas-Armas et al., 2024).

1.1.5 Saponins and tannins

Saponins (glycosylated triterpenes/steroids) and condensed tannins (proanthocyanidins) are widely reported in qualitative phytochemical screenings and account for some of the astringent and surface-active properties of leaf extracts (Alwaleed et al., 2025). They contribute to antimicrobial effects (membrane disruption) and to binding of dietary lipids and proteins (Liga et al., 2025).

1.1.6 Terpenoids, carotenoids and tocopherols

Moringa oleifera leaf carotenoids (β -carotene, lutein, zeaxanthin) and tocopherols (vitamin E homologs) are important antioxidants and nutritional components. Terpenoids and triterpenes (e.g., oleanolic and ursolic acid derivatives) appear in nonpolar fractions and are commonly reported in GC-MS and LC-MS profiling (Rojas-Armas et al., 2024). Fatty acid profiling shows substantial oleic acid in leaf lipids when measured in oil fractions (Monogna & Margesan, 2024; Buyel, 2025).

1.1.7 Sterols

Phytosterols such as β -sitosterol and its glycosides are consistently reported in *Moringa oleifera* leaves and may contribute to lipid-lowering effects by interfering with intestinal cholesterol absorption (Divya et al., 2024).

1.1.8 Vitamins, amino acids, minerals and other nutrients

Moringa oleifera leaves are rich in vitamins (vitamin C, folates, provitamin A carotenoids), essential amino acids (high protein content per dry weight), and minerals (Ca, K, Fe, Mg). While these are nutritional rather than classical secondary metabolites, they interact with phytochemicals and influence net biological effects (Bhalla et al., 2021; Greco et al., 2025).

1.2 Notable individual compounds in *Moringa oleifera* leaves and their significance

1.2.1 Quercetin & kaempferol (and glycosides): Major flavonoids; strong antioxidants and modulators of inflammatory signaling (Patil et al., 2022).

1.2.2 Chlorogenic acid: Abundant phenolic acid with antioxidant and metabolic-modulatory actions (Patil et al., 2022; Divya et al., 2024).

1.2.3 Glucomoringin → moringin (isothiocyanate): Unique to *Moringa* genus; potent bioactivities including neuroprotective and anticancer effects described in recent mechanistic studies (El-Sherbiny et al., 2024).

1.2.4 Niazimicin/Niazirin: Sulfur-containing compounds linked to chemopreventive activity.

1.2.5 β -sitosterol: Common plant sterol, implicated in cholesterol-modulating effects (Patil et al., 2022).

Flavonoids, phenolic acids, carotenoids and tocopherols have antioxidant activity- scavenge radicals and chelate metals. Multiple recent studies (Ali et al., 2020; Patil et al., 2022; Terngu et al., 2024; Ugosor & Ornguga, 2025; Ugosor & Wada, 2025) confirm antibacterial activity of leaf extracts against foodborne and clinical strains. Certain phenolics and sterols may contribute to lipid-lowering and glycemic modulation through enzyme inhibition (e.g., α -glucosidase) and modulation of signaling pathways. Moringin and related isothiocyanates are implicated in protective effects against oxidative neuronal injury and in preclinical cancer models (Otman et al., 2019; Patil et al., 2022; Ugosor & Ornguga, 2025).

1.3 Mechanism of Action of *Moringa oleifera* Phytochemicals on Antimicrobial Activity

The antimicrobial potency of *Moringa oleifera* has been widely attributed to its rich composition of bioactive phytochemicals such as alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and terpenoids. These compounds exhibit diverse mechanisms of action that compromise microbial viability through structural damage, enzyme inhibition, oxidative stress, and disruption of genetic and metabolic processes (Chis et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024; Alwaleed et al., 2025; Ugosor & Wada, 2025).

1.3.1 Alkaloids

Alkaloids present in *Moringa oleifera*, including moringinine and related derivatives, play a significant role in antimicrobial defense. These nitrogenous bases disrupt microbial cell membranes by inserting into lipid bilayers, thereby increasing permeability and inducing leakage of cellular contents (Chuang et al., 2007; Ugosor & Wada, 2025). Additionally, alkaloids can inhibit bacterial DNA topoisomerase and gyrase enzymes, interfering with DNA replication and transcription (Kumar et al., 2012). They may also suppress quorum sensing, limiting microbial communication, biofilm formation, and virulence expression (Cushnie et al., 2014; Ugosor & Ornguga, 2025).

1.3.2 Phenolic Compounds and Flavonoids

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids such as quercetin, kaempferol, and chlorogenic acid are abundant in *Moringa oleifera* extracts and contribute significantly to its antimicrobial activity. These compounds act as strong antioxidants, generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) that cause oxidative damage to microbial lipids, proteins, and DNA (Awaleed et al., 2025). They also chelate essential metal ions such as Fe^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , which are critical cofactors for microbial enzymatic systems, thereby impairing metabolism and growth (Wang et al., 2024; Ugosor & Wada, 2025). Furthermore,

flavonoids interact with microbial cell walls, altering membrane permeability and leading to leakage of intracellular contents (Othman et al., 2019; Ugosor & Ornguga, 2025).

1.3.3 Saponins

Saponins, amphiphilic glycosides present in *Moringa oleifera*, exert their antimicrobial effects mainly by targeting microbial membranes. They interact with sterols such as ergosterol (in fungi) and phospholipids (in bacteria), leading to pore formation and cell membrane disruption (Alietal.,2020; Ugosor & Ornguga, 2025). The resulting leakage of essential ions and metabolites causes osmotic imbalance and microbial cell death. Moreover, saponins enhance the permeability of microbial membranes, facilitating the entry of other antimicrobial compounds within the extract (Oluwatosin et al., 2020).

1.3.4 Tannins

Tannins are polyphenolic compounds capable of precipitating microbial proteins and disrupting cell wall integrity. They form hydrogen bonds with bacterial adhesins, enzymes, and transport proteins, thereby interfering with nutrient uptake and energy metabolism (Wang et al., 2024; Ugosor & Ornguga, 2025). Tannins also inactivate microbial enzymes by forming irreversible complexes, leading to loss of function and cell lysis (Banso et al., 2007). Furthermore, their ability to bind to the peptidoglycan layer of bacteria results in structural deformation and increased susceptibility to osmotic stress (Butel et al., 2025; Ugosor & Wada, 2025).

1.3.5 Terpenoids and Glycosides

Terpenoids and glycosides in *Moringa oleifera* exhibit antimicrobial activity through membrane disruption and enzyme inhibition. Terpenoids increase microbial membrane permeability and interfere with respiratory chain enzymes, leading to reduced Adenosine Triphosphate (ATP) synthesis (Deepali et al., 2025). Glycosides, on the other hand, can inhibit bacterial energy metabolism and affect protein synthesis by interfering with ribosomal function (Oluwatosin et al., 2020). These compounds may also possess quorum-sensing inhibitory properties, reducing microbial communication and virulence factor production (Ademiluyi et al., 2018; Butel et al., 2025).

1.4 Synergistic Antimicrobial Effects

The antimicrobial efficacy of *Moringa oleifera* is enhanced by the synergistic interactions among its phytochemicals. For example, saponins increase membrane permeability, enabling the entry of alkaloids and phenolics, while flavonoids and tannins act concurrently on microbial enzymes and structural proteins. Such multi-target interactions provide *Moringa oleifera* with broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria as well as fungi (Khalafalla et al., 2010; Othman et al., 2019; Ugosor & Wada, 2025).

1.5 Safety, stability, and processing considerations

Many bioactive compounds are heat-sensitive (e.g., some glucosinolates/isothiocyanates and vitamin C). Drying and high-temperature processing change the nutritional and bioactive profiles (Rojas-

Armas et al., 2024; Divya et al., 2024). Myrosinase activity is essential for conversion of glucosinolates to isothiocyanates as thermal inactivation alters bioavailability and downstream activity.

Generally, *Moringa oleifera* leaves products consumed in customary culinary amounts are considered safe. However, concentrated extracts and high doses require toxicological evaluation (dose, preparation, and contaminants). Recent toxicology and safety reviews highlight the need for standardization.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Collection and Preparation

Fresh leaves of *Moringa oleifera* were collected from a local farm, washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove dust and debris, and shade-dried for 7 days. The dried leaves were ground into fine powder using an electric blender and stored in airtight containers until use.

2.2 Extraction Procedure

About 100 g of the powdered leaf material was soaked separately in 500 mL of distilled water for 72 hours with occasional stirring. The mixture was then filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 45°C. The crude extract was stored at 4°C until analysis (Harborne, 1998).

2.3 Qualitative Phytochemical Screening

The extracts were tested for the presence of major secondary metabolites using standard qualitative procedures. Reagent preparation and stepwise procedures follow Harborne (1998) and Trease & Evans (2002).

2.3.1 Test for Alkaloids: Mayer's, Harger's, Dragendorff's, and Wagner's reagents.

About 2 mL of the extract was dissolved in 5 mL of dilute hydrochloric acid, warmed, and filtered. The filtrate was then divided into four portions and each reagent added separately. The observation of orange/brown, creamy, reddish-brown, and yellow precipitates with Dragendorff's, Mayer's, Wagner's, and Hager's reagents respectively indicated the presence of alkaloids.

2.3.2 Flavonoids

(a) Shinoda's test: Five drops of hydrochloric acid was added to 2 mL of the extract in a test tube, followed by 0.5 g of magnesium turnings. The observation of red/pink colouration confirmed the presence of flavonoids.

(b) Alkaline reagent test: 10 % sodium hydroxide was added to 1 mL of the extract in a test tube, followed by 3 drops of dilute HCl. A yellow colouration indicated the presence of flavonoids.

2.3.3 Tannins

(a) Ferric chloride test: Three drops of 5 % FeCl₃ solution was added to 2 mL of the extract in a test tube. A blue-black or greenish-black colour showed the presence of tannins

(b) Lead acetate tests: Three drops of 10 % lead acetate solution was added to 2 mL of the extract in a test tube. The formation of white or yellowish precipitates confirmed tannins.

(c) Gelatin test: To 2 mL of the extract in a test tube, 3 drops of 1 % gelatin solution containing sodium hydroxide, followed by 3 drops of dilute HCl. Formation of white precipitates or cloudiness indicated the presence of tannins.

2.3.4 Saponins

Froth/ Emulsion test: To 2 ml of the extract, 5 mL of distilled water was added in a test tube, shaken vigorously for five minutes, and allowed to stand. The observation of persistent froth (1-2 cm height) was observed. Next, 3 drops of olive oil was added to the froth. The formation of emulsion indicated the presence of saponins.

2.3.5 Phenolics

Ferric chloride test: Three drops of 5 % FeCl₃ was added to 2 mL of the extract in a test tube. A deep blue colour confirmed the presence of phenolics.

2.3.6 Steroids

(a) Liebermann-Buchard test: To 2 mL of acetic anhydride and 1 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ acid in a test tube, 2 mL of the extract was added. A green or bluish-green colour indicated the presence of steroids.

(b) Salkowski's test: To 5 mL of chloroform in a test tube, 2 mL of the extract was mixed. Then, 2 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ acid was added and shaken gently. A reddish-brown colour indicated the presence of steroidal ring (i.e. the glycone portion) of the glycoside.

2.3.7 Cardiac glycosides

(a) Keller-Killiani test: To 2 mL of the extract, 1 mL of glacial acetic acid and 1 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ were added. Formation of a brown ring at the interface indicated the presence of glycosides.

(b) Legal's test: To 2 mL of the extract in a test tube, add three drops of Legal's reagent (solution of sodium nitroprusside and sodium hydroxide). A positive result was indicated by a pink to red colour.

2.3.8 Terpenoids

Salkowski test: To 2 mL of chloroform in a test tube, 3 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ acid was added to form a layer. A reddish-brown colouration at the interface indicated the presence of terpenoids.

2.4 Quantitative Phytochemical Determination

Spectrophotometric assays were used to quantify total phenolics (Folin–Ciocalteu method), flavonoids (AlCl₃ method), and tannins (Folin–Denis method). Where appropriate, assays were calibrated against standards and results were expressed as mg equivalents per gramme of extract.

2.4.1 Determination of alkaloids

Gravimetric method: 5 g of the extract was weighed and dissolved in 200 mL of 10 % acetic acid in ethanol. This was allowed to stand for 4 hours. Thereafter, the mixture was concentrated to one-quarter volume on a water bath. Concentrated ammonium hydroxide was added until precipitation was complete. The precipitates was then washed with dilute NH₄OH and dried to constant weight. The percentage of alkaloid content was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ alkaloid content} = \left(\frac{\text{Weight of residue}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \right) \times 100 \%$$

2.4.2 Determination of flavonoids

Aluminium Chloride, AlCl₃ Colorimetric method: 1 mL of the extract was mixed with 1 mL of 2 % AlCl₃ in methanol and incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes. The absorbance of the resulting mixture was measured at 420 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Quercetin was used as standard and the result was expressed as mg Quercetin Equivalent (QE)/g extract.

2.4.3 Determination of tannins

Folin-Denis or Vanillin-HCl method: One mL of the extract was mixed with 5 mL of Folin-Denis reagent and 10 mL of sodium carbonate (35 % in a test tube). The mixture was incubated at 25 °C for 30 minutes and the absorbance measured at 760 nm. The result was expressed as mg Tannic Acid Equivalent (TAE)/g extract.

2.4.4 Determination of Saponins

Gravimetric method: Into 100 mL of 20 % ethanol, 5 g of the extract was dissolved for 4 hours at 55 °C. The filtrate was filtered using NO.1 Whatman filter paper. The residues were re-extracted with 200 mL ethanol. The filtrates were combined, concentrated to 40 mL on a water bath, and extracted with diethyl ether. Next, 20 mL of n-butanol, wash with 5 % NaCl solution, and evaporate to constant weight on a water bath. The % saponin = $\frac{\text{Weight of residue}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100 \%$

2.4.5 Determination of total phenolic content

Folin-Ciocalteu method: One mL of the extract was mixed with 5 mL of 10 % Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 4 mL of 7.5 % Na₂CO₃. The mixture was then incubated at 40 °C for 30 minutes and the absorbance measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 765 nm. The result was expressed as mg Gallic Acid Equivalent (GAE)/g extract.

2.4.6 Determination of steroids

Spectrophotometric method: One mL of the extract was mixed with 2 mL chloroform, 2 mL acetic anhydride, and 1 mL concentrated H₂SO₄. This was allowed to stand for 30 minutes and the absorbance measured using a spectrophotometer at 420 nm. Steroids was expressed as mg cholesterol equivalent per gramme.

2.4.7 Determination of glycosides

Anthrone method: Into a clean test tube, 1.0 mL of extract was placed and 4.0 mL anthrone reagent (0.2 % in concentrated H₂SO₄) was carefully added. The mixture was mixed gently by inverting once and immediately placed in a boiling water bath at 100 °C for 8 minutes. The test tube was then removed and cooled rapidly in an ice bath for 5 minutes to stop development. It was then, transferred into a cuvette and measured at 620 nm against a reagent blank (1 mL distilled water + 4 mL anthrone reagent, treated identically). Calibration curve was done by preparing glucose standards (20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/mL). For each standard 1.0 mL was pipetted into a clean test tube and 4.0 mL anthrone reagent was added, heated for 8 minutes, cooled and absorbance measured at 620 nm. A plot of absorbance (y) vs concentration (x, µg/mL) to obtain the regression line: $y = mx + b$ and compute the concentration (C_o in the reacted aliquot):

$C_{\text{extract}} (\mu\text{g/ml}) = \frac{A_{\text{sample}} - b}{m}$. The result was expressed as mg GE/g.

2.4.8 Determination of terpenoids

Gravimetric method

To 50 mL of distilled water in a beaker, 5 mL of the extract was added and boiled for 30 minutes. The mixture was allowed to cool, filtered using No.1 Whatman filter paper, and transferred into a separatory funnel. Next, 50 mL of petroleum ether was added to the filtrate, shaken vigorously, allowed to separate (phase separation) and the upper organic layer was collected. This procedure was repeated twice and the organic layer combined. The organic layer was evaporated in a pre-weighed beaker (w₁) at 40 °C over a rotary evaporator. The beaker was then placed in a desiccator for 30 minutes and weighed with the residue (W₂). The % terpenoid was estimated as follows:

$\text{Terpenoid (\% w/w)} = \frac{\text{Weight of extract}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100\% = \frac{(W_2 - W_1)}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100\%$

2.5 Antimicrobial Assay

The antimicrobial activities of the extract was tested against eleven fungi: *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus tamari*, *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, *Penicillium marneffeii*, *Myrothecium verrucaria*, *Rhizopus nigrican*, *Rhizopus stolonifera*, *Fuussarium oxysporum*, *Fussarium solani*, *Candida albicans* and seven bacteria: *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Serrtia marcescens*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Erwinia carotovora*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniaeus* using disc method as described by Terngu et al (2024) without modification.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined using serial dilution/micro-dilution in nutrient broth using concentrations of 25 mg/mL, 12.5 mg/mL, 6.25 mg/mL and 3.13 mg/mL of the extract as described by Terngu et al (2024) without modification. Triplicate wells were also prepared for the respective concentrations of the antimicrobial agents. Isolates suspension of 10⁶ cells/mL each were pipetted into each well and incubated overnight at 37 °C. After this period, the turbidity of the wells were observed and noted. The least concentration of the antimicrobial agents which prevented the visible growth of the isolates was noted as the Minimum Inhibition Concentration.

2.6 Statistical Analysis

All assays were performed in triplicate (n = 3). Results were expressed as Mean \pm SD and analyzed using ANOVA. Mean separation was done using Duncan's Multiple Range Test at a 5 % significance level.

3.0 Results

3.1 Phytochemical Composition

Table 1: Result of phytochemical analysis

Secondary Metabolite	Test	Result
Alkaloids	Mayer's Test	
	Drangendorff's Test	+
	Wagner's Test	+
Flavonoids	Shinoda's Test	+
	Alkaline Test	+
Saponins	Froth/Emulsion Test	+
Phenolics	Ferric Chloride Test	+
Steroids	Salkwoski's Test	+
	Libbermann Burchard's Test	+
	Keller-Killiani's Test	+
Glycosides	Legal's Test	+
	Borntrager's Test	+
Terpenoids	Salkwoski's Test	+

Key: + = Presence of secondary metabolite

Table 2: Quantitative phytochemical analysis result

Phytochemical	Quantity
Alkaloids	1.0 % (w/w)
Flavonoids	80.10 mg QE/g
Saponins	6.20 % (w/w)
Phenolics	110.8 mg GAE/g
Steroids	0.7 mg CE/g
Glycosides	5.8 mg GE/g
Terpenoids	4.3 % (w/w)

3.2 Antimicrobial Activity

Table 3: Antimicrobial sensitivity test result

	Concentration (mg/mL)				
	100	75	50	25	Control
Fungi					

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<i>A. niger</i>	7.81 ^a ± 0.01	6.83 ^b ± 0.00	5.83 ^c ± 0.02	4.87 ^d ± 0.02	8.21 ^e ± 0.01
<i>A. flavus</i>	7.91 ^a ± 0.01	7.50 ^b ± 0.01	6.33 ^c ± 0.01	5.92 ^d ± 0.01	9.87 ^e ± 0.01
<i>A. tamari</i>	8.82 ^a ± 0.01	7.90 ^b ± 0.02	6.91 ^c ± 0.01	5.01 ^d ± 0.02	10.31 ^e ± 0.02
<i>B. theobromae</i>	8.12 ^a ± 0.01	7.50 ^b ± 0.01	6.70 ^c ± 0.02	5.90 ^d ± 0.01	10.95 ^e ± 0.01
<i>P. marneffeii</i>	9.12 ^a ± 0.01	8.95 ^b ± 0.02	7.54 ^c ± 0.01	6.70 ^d ± 0.01	13.15 ^e ± 0.01
<i>M. verrucaria</i>	10.16 ^a ± 0.02	9.10 ^b ± 0.03	8.90 ^c ± 0.02	7.89 ^d ± 0.02	12.42 ^e ± 0.02
<i>R. nigrican</i>	11.81 ^a ± 0.02	10.10 ^b ± 0.02	9.00 ^c ± 0.03	8.14 ^d ± 0.02	14.16 ^e ± 0.02
<i>R. stolenifera</i>	13.60 ^a ± 0.01	11.16 ^b ± 0.01	9.50 ^c ± 0.01	7.80 ^d ± 0.01	18.00 ^e ± 0.01
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	20.50 ^a ± 0.02	18.33 ^b ± 0.02	17.33 ^c ± 0.01	15.93 ^d ± 0.01	24.67 ^e ± 0.02
<i>F. solani</i>	19.98 ^a ± 0.01	17.87 ^b ± 0.01	15.2 ^c ± 0.02	13.45 ^d ± 0.01	22.45 ^e ± 0.02
<i>C. albicans</i>	19.10 ^a ± 0.20	16.60 ^b ± 0.30	13.80 ^c ± 0.20	11.50 ^d ± 0.20	30.10 ^e ± 0.20

Bacteria

<i>K. oxytoca</i>	25.60 ^a ± 0.02	23.9 ^b ± 0.01	20.36 ^c ± 0.01	18.67 ^d ± 0.02	30.83 ^e ± 0.02
<i>S. marcescens</i>	32.67 ^a ± 0.01	29.00 ^b ± 0.01	27.33 ^c ± 0.01	25.39 ^d ± 0.02	39.56 ^e ± 0.01
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	37.26 ^a ± 0.02	34.89 ^b ± 0.02	31.93 ^c ± 0.01	28.38 ^d ± 0.01	45.67 ^e ± 0.01
<i>E. coli</i>	40.28 ^a ± 0.02	38.10 ^b ± 0.02	35.89 ^c ± 0.02	35.12 ^d ± 0.01	50.12 ^e ± 0.02
<i>E. carotovora</i>	52.24 ^a ± 0.01	48.89 ^b ± 0.01	45.13 ^c ± 0.02	42.98 ^d ± 0.02	63.19 ^e ± 0.01
<i>S. aureus</i>	23.50 ^a ± 0.20	19.90 ^b ± 0.20	16.50 ^c ± 0.20	14.20 ^d ± 0.30	40.10 ^e ± 0.20
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	21.60 ^a ± 0.20	18.80 ^b ± 0.30	15.90 ^c ± 0.20	12.80 ^d ± 0.20	35.56 ^e ± 0.20

N=5: Means followed by different alphabetical letters (superscript) within the same row are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) according to ANOVA and Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

Table 4: Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) Test Result

Test Organisms	Concentration (mg/mL)					MIC
	25.0	12.50	6.25	3.13	1.57	
Fungi						
<i>A. niger</i>	-	-	-	+	++	6.25
<i>A. flavus</i>	-	-	-	+	++	6.25
<i>A. tamari</i>	-	-	-	++	+++	6.25
<i>B. theobromae</i>	-	-	-	+	++	6.25
<i>P. marneffeii</i>	-	-	-	++	+++	6.25
<i>M. verrucaria</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>R. nigrican</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>R. stolenifera</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>F. solani</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>C. albicans</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
Bacteria						
<i>K. oxytoca</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>S. marcescens</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>E. coli</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>S. aureus</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	-	-	-	-	+	3.13

Key:

+ = Growth

++ = Moderate growth

+++ = Significant growth

- = No growth

4.0 Discussion

Qualitative screening (Table 1) revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, phenolics, steroids, terpenoids, and glycosides in the extract. This result is in agreement with that of other researchers (Ali et al., 2020; Bhulla et al., 2021; Divya et al., 2024; El-Sherbiny et al., 2024). Quantitative results (Table 2) indicated high concentrations of total phenolics and flavonoids, confirming *M. oleifera*'s rich antioxidant potential. This result is concurrent with that of Younis et al (2022), Kashyap et al (2022), Setyani et al (2023), Wang et al (2024), and Deepali et al (2025) where varying amounts of the phytochemicals were recorded. The presence of abundant phenolic and flavonoid compounds in *M. oleifera* extracts correlates strongly with their antimicrobial potency.

These bioactive compounds are known to disrupt microbial cell walls, interfere with nucleic acid synthesis, and inhibit enzymatic activity.

Table 3 showed antimicrobial sensitivity test result, while Table 4 revealed the MIC of the extract against the pure isolates. Antimicrobial sensitivity assay of the extract revealed a broad-spectrum inhibitory effect against both fungal and bacterial isolates ranging from 52.24 ± 0.01 mm (*Erwinia carotovora*) at 100 mg/mL to 4.87 ± 0.02 mm (*Aspergillus niger*) at 25 mg/mL. Among the fungal species, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium oxysporum solani*, and *Candida albicans* demonstrated the largest zones of inhibition (up to 20.50 mm, 19.98 mm, and 19.10 mm, respectively, at 100 mg/mL), indicating strong antifungal potential. Other species such as *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, and *Botryodiplodia theobromae* showed moderate sensitivity, suggesting variability in susceptibility among different fungal taxa. In contrast, the antibacterial results revealed comparatively higher sensitivity in Gram-negative bacteria (*E.coli*, *P.aeruginosa*, *E.carotovora*) and some filamentous fungi (*F.oxysporum*, *F.solani*) than in Gram-positive strains (*S.aureus*, *K. pneumonia* and some *Aspergillus* spp. *Erwinia carotovora*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* exhibited particularly large inhibition zones (52.24 mm, 40.28 mm, and 37.26 mm, respectively, at 100 mg/mL), whereas *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* displayed weaker responses.

The MIC result (Table 4) values ranged between 6.25 and 3.13 mg/mL depending on the organism, with activity increasing proportionally to concentration. The result showed that *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus tamari*, *Botryodiplodia theobromae*, and *Penicillium marneffeii* all recorded an MIC of 6.25 mg/mL, while the other isolates registered MIC of 3.13 mg/mL. This result suggests that the extract retains antimicrobial activity at relatively low concentrations.

The observed dose-dependent inhibition trend across all microorganisms confirms that antimicrobial activity is concentration-dependent. Collectively, these findings suggest that *Moringa oleifera* contains bioactive constituents capable of inhibiting a wide range of pathogenic microbes, with notable efficacy against Gram-negative bacteria and filamentous fungi. Such findings validate the traditional use of *Moringa oleifera* in herbal medicine for treating infections.

5.0 Conclusion

The study demonstrates that *Moringa oleifera* leaves contain a rich and functionally diverse bioactive compounds dominated by flavonoids, phenolic compounds, glycosides, saponins, steroids, and terpenoids with significant nutritional and health benefits as well as antioxidant and microbial activities. The high inhibition zones against the test microorganisms are likely due to its higher content of phenolic and flavonoid compounds. These results support the use of *M. oleifera* as a natural source of antimicrobial agents and justify further studies toward isolating, characterizing, dose-response toxicology of its active components, and clinical trials that can link specific leaf phytochemicals to define human outcomes for potential pharmaceutical, antimicrobial, nutritional and health benefits.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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